

Polarography of Acetophenone*

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The polarographic reduction of acetophenone at pH 10.3 in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol medium, containing 0.1 M tetramethylammonium bromide as the supporting electrolyte and 0.03% gelatin as the maximum suppresser has been studied in detail. The reduction process is diffusion-controlled and irreversible in nature. The heterogeneous rate constant $k_{p,h}$ and αn_a have been calculated at different temperatures. The thermodynamic parameters such as the enthalpy of activation (ΔH), free energy of activation (ΔG) and the entropy of activation (ΔS) for the electrode process have been calculated. The free energy of activation of diffusion Q_D and the radius (r) of the solvated depolarizer have been determined and discussed.

ALKYL aryl ketones and diaryl ketones are reduced at dropping mercury electrode in acidic media following the sequences proton, electron, electron, proton. In the medium pH range the sequence is electron, proton, electron, proton and in alkaline media the path is electron, electron, two protons. In the intermediate pH ranges, the current is governed by the rate of protonation of the carbonyl compound or the radical anion. In the protonation of the ketones, proton donors other than hydronium ion can participate. Simple pH-dependence can be obtained only in buffers containing a constant concentration of the basic component of the buffer². Recently, we have investigated³ the polarographic reduction of certain ketones in acidic media of different pH with a view to elucidating the group constants C_1 and their relationship with the structures of carbonyl compounds applying quantum mechanical treatment. Though the course of the polarographic study of various ketones has been made rather extensively, in most investigations attention has been paid only to a certain aspect of the problem. In the present investigation we report the polarographic reduction of acetophenone at pH 10.3 comprising its electrode kinetics, the effect of concentration and the effective mercury pressure head on the mode of reduction.

Experimental

Acetophenone was fractionally frozen thrice and the solid was distilled under reduced pressure. Ethanol, mercurous chloride (A. R.), mercury, tetramethylammonium bromide (B. D. H) and gelatin were purified following the literature methods. The nitrogen gas used for expelling dissolved oxygen was from a cylinder containing 99.9% pure nitrogen, and was purified by a modification of the procedure of Kolthoff⁴. Viscosity was measured using Ostwald viscometer taking the viscosity coefficient of water as reference. Density was measured using a

10 ml specific gravity bottle. The viscosity coefficients of water used for calculation were 0.7208, 0.6536 and 0.5970 centipoise at 35, 40 and 45°, respectively.

All the solutions were kept in a thermostat, with an accuracy $\pm 0.05^\circ$, atleast for 1 hr before the polarogram was run. The experimental solution was de-oxygenated by passing the purified nitrogen for 15-20 min. The polarograms of various solutions were obtained with ELICO CL 25 automatic recording polarograph having LR 101P recorder. The potentials were measured against a saturated calomel electrode (SCE). The dropping mercury electrode (dme) had the following characteristics at a mercury height of 65 cm, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 1.4847 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/2}$, in a solution containing 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol and 0.1 M tetramethylammonium bromide.

Throughout the measurements, the current at the end of the drop life was taken instead of the average current because the determination of the kinetic parameters is based on the Koutecky's calculations which are more accurately reproduced by measuring the maximum current⁵. The half-wave potentials ($E_{1/2}$) were calculated by the log plot method.

Results and Discussions

Acetophenone gets reduced at the dropping mercury electrode giving a well defined single wave (Fig. 1) in the basic medium of pH 10.3. The height of the wave is not apparently influenced by changing the pH of the medium. The diffusion current I_d varies linearly with the concentration of the depolarizer in the range $1.25 \times 10^{-4} M$ to $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ (Table 1). The half-wave potential of the reduction wave shifts to more negative potential on increasing the concentration of the depolarizer. Polarograms were also recorded at various heights of mercury

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Fig. 1. Polarogram of acetophenone at pH 10.8 in a medium of 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol containing 0.1 M tetramethylammonium bromide as supporting electrolyte and 0.03% gelatin as maximum suppressor.

TABLE 1—HALF-WAVE POTENTIAL AND DIFFUSION CURRENT OF ACETOPHENONE AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS

Concentration $C \times 10^4 \text{ M}$	$-E_{1/2}$ V	I_d μA	$\frac{I_d}{C} \times 10^4$ $\mu\text{A mole}^{-1}$
1.25	1.350	0.487	3.896
2.50	1.432	0.975	3.900
3.40	1.558	1.275	3.750
5.00	1.654	1.875	3.750
10.00	1.662	3.675	3.675
20.00	1.706	7.350	3.675

reservoir in order to determine the effect of the pressure of mercury head on the nature of the polarographic wave. It has been noticed that the diffusion current varies linearly with the square-root of the effective mercury height (h_{eff}) (Table 2).

TABLE 2—DIFFUSION CURRENT OF ACETOPHENONE AT VARIOUS HEIGHT OF MERCURY

h_{appl} cm	h_{eff} cm	I_d μA	$I_d/h_{eff}^{1/2}$
30	28.22	1.350	0.254
35	33.22	1.575	0.273
40	38.22	1.725	0.279
45	43.22	1.762	0.268
50	48.22	1.837	0.265
55	53.22	1.875	0.257
60	58.22	1.912	0.251

The slope values of the plot of $E_{d.e.}$ vs $\log \left(\frac{i}{I_d - i} \right)$ obtained for the reduction of acetophenone is

0.0610 V which is higher than that required theoretically and the intercept gives the half-wave potential as -1.654 V at 35° .

The number of electrons involved in the electrode process was obtained employing Ilkovic equation

$$n = I_d / 607 D^{1/2} cm^{2/3} t^{1/6}$$

and Stock-Einstein equation

$$D = 2.96 \times 10^{-7} / \eta (V_m)^{1/3} cm^2 sec^{-1}$$

where η = solution viscosity in dyne-seconds per sq.cm and V_m = molar volume. Substituting the value of η of 50% (v/v) ethanol containing 0.1 M tetramethylammonium bromide and 0.03% gelatin, n gets a value of 2.21. Hence, the value of n involved in the polarographic reduction of acetophenone was taken to be 2.

The polarograms run at different temperatures show that the half-wave potential of acetophenone is -1.654 , -1.650 and -1.646 V at 35, 40 and 45, respectively. The corresponding diffusion currents are 1.875, 2.100 and 2.550 μA . The temperature coefficient of diffusion current is found to be $3.43\% \text{ deg}^{-1}$. The activation energy of diffusion Q_D has been calculated using the following equation⁶

$$\log \frac{I_d}{m^{2/3} t^{1/6}} = \log 0.627 n F D^{1/2} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{Q_D}{3.03 RT} \quad (1)$$

where Q_D is the activation energy of diffusion. The activation energy of diffusion for acetophenone is 5.63 Kcal.

On graphical analysis, it has been found that diffusion current constant is related to diffusion coefficients by the parabolic law $I_d \propto D^{1/2}$. This conclusion is in agreement with the theoretical Ilkovic equation. On the other hand, the diffusion coefficients deduced from viscosity data vary with an increase in the concentration of ethanol. Practically no change has been observed in the polarographic characteristics when acetophenone is reduced at varying pH values (10.3, 11.5 and 13.6).

An analysis of the polarographic wave of acetophenone shows that the current is diffusion-controlled as it varies linearly with the concentration and also with the square-root of the effective mercury head. The small value of temperature coefficient of the diffusion current also confirms the diffusion-controlled nature of the wave.

The slope value obtained from the logarithmic analysis of the wave is higher than the value required theoretically, showing that the reduction takes place irreversibly. The variation of half-wave potential with concentration and the shift of half-wave potential towards more positive side with rise in temperature prove the reduction to take place irreversibly. The shift in half-wave potential towards more positive value shows easier reduction of the compound at higher temperature and is in accordance with irreversible nature of the process.

Since the half-wave potential for the single wave of acetophenone is independent of pH, the process

is probably one in which the electron enters first, followed by an irreversible extraction of proton from the solvent. As the polarographic reduction process consumes two electrons per molecule of acetophenone, the final product must be the corresponding alcohol. This holds irrespective of whether reduction takes place in one or two steps. Based on all the experimental facts, the mechanism of the polarographic reduction may be formulated as

and it is the result of two-electron, two-proton process.

The current corresponding to the foot of the wave is independent of mercury head whereas at the top of the wave (i.e., at the limiting current values) it is proportional to $h^{1/2}$. This is evident from the plots (Fig. 2) of $(i/h_0)^{1/2}$ vs $(i/i_0)_m$. The transient dependence of current on the mercury head has also been studied in terms of $\log i$ vs $\log h$ plots, depicted in Fig. 3. It is evident from these plots that the slope of 'log-log' plot is zero at the potential corresponding to the foot of the wave and it gradually increases to 0.5 as the potential corresponding to the limiting current is reached and in between the two extremes the slope varies from 0 to 0.5. This confirms that while the current is totally kinetically controlled at the foot of the wave it becomes diffusion-controlled at the top and in between the two both the rate of electron transfer and diffusion determine the magnitude of the current.

The application of Delahay's treatment⁷ at the foot of the wave ($\gamma < 0.2$; γ is the ratio i/i_0) gives $kD^{-1/2} < 0.05 \text{ sec}^{-1/2}$ showing very small contribution of electrode kinetics to the current measured.

The kinetic parameters (transfer coefficient, αn_a and the heterogeneous rate constant, $k_{r,h}^0$) have been

Fig. 2. Effect of variation of mercury pressure head on the maximum current at various stages in the reduction wave of acetophenone.

Fig. 3. Log-log plots of current and mercury pressure head for acetophenone.

calculated by Koutecky's⁸ theoretical treatment as extended by Meites and Israel⁹, at different temperatures, when the potential is measured against saturated calomel electrode (ex : at 35°)

$$E_{d,e} + 0.2344 = \frac{0.0611}{\alpha n_a} \log \frac{1.349 k_{r,h}^0 t^{1/2}}{D^{1/2}} - \frac{0.0560}{\alpha n_a} \log \frac{i}{(I_d - i)} \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\text{and } E_{1/2} = \frac{0.0611}{\alpha n_a} \log \frac{1.349 k_{r,h}^0 t^{1/2}}{D^{1/2}} \quad \dots (3)$$

Since the drop-time, t , does not vary appreciably over the range of potential applied by the rising part of the wave in the case of the reduction of acetophenone, it was considered unnecessary to apply the correction for drop-time. Hence, if t is constant and independent of potential, a plot of $E_{d,e}$ vs $\log \left(\frac{i}{I_d - i} \right)$ should be linear and should have a slope equal to $-\frac{0.0560}{\alpha n_a}$, $-\frac{0.0569}{\alpha n_a}$ and $-\frac{0.0578}{\alpha n_a}$ volt at 35, 40 and 45°, respectively. The enthalpy of activation (ΔH) for the electrode reaction has been calculated by equating the slope of $\log k_{r,h}^0$ vs $1/T$ plot to $-\Delta H/2.303 R$ and is found to be 71.06 Kcal mole⁻¹.

The potential dependent heterogeneous rate constant $k_{r,h}$ is related to E by the following two equations^{10,11}

$$k_{r,h} = k_{r,h}^0 \exp \left[-\alpha n_a F(E + 0.2412)/RT \right] \quad \dots (4)$$

$$k_{r,h} = \frac{KT}{h} \phi \exp \left[-\Delta G + \alpha n_a F(E + 0.2417)/RT \right] \dots (5)$$

Equating the value of $\log k_{r,h}$ at $E=0$ from the two relations we get ΔG , the free energy of activation, which is obtained by the relation

$$k_{r,h}^0 = \frac{KT}{h} \phi \exp \left[\frac{-\Delta G}{RT} \right] \quad (6)$$

where K = Boltzman constant, h = Planck's constant,

$\phi = 2.0 \times 10^{-8}$ cm and the other terms have their usual meanings. The free energy of activation for the polarographic reduction of acetophenone, is found to be 41.20 Kcal mole⁻¹. The entropy of activation (ΔS) is found to be 95.40 cal deg⁻¹ mole⁻¹. The various polarographic parameters obtained for acetophenone at different temperatures are given in Tables 3 and 4.

TABLE 3—POLAROGRAPHIC PARAMETERS OF ACETOPHENONE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temp. °C	$-E_{1/2}$ V	αn_a	$k_{p,h}^0$ cm sec ⁻¹	$D \times 10^6$ cm ² sec ⁻¹	$k_{p,h}^0 D^{-1/2}$ sec ^{-1/2}
35	1.654	0.9180	3.528×10^{-25}	4.328	1.696×10^{-22}
40	1.650	0.9017	2.069×10^{-24}	5.429	8.879×10^{-23}
45	1.646	0.8898	1.356×10^{-23}	8.005	4.791×10^{-21}

TABLE 4—DIFFUSION CURRENT CONSTANT, RADIUS, DIFFUSION CURRENT AND FREE ENERGY OF REDUCTION OF ACETOPHENONE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temp. °C	I μ A M ⁻¹ mg ^{-2/3} sec ^{1/3}	$r \times 10^9$ cm	I_d μ A	ΔG Kcal mole ⁻¹
35	2.526	3.28	1.875	41.63
40	2.829	2.97	2.100	41.24
45	3.435	2.39	2.550	40.72

A perusal of the values of αn_a in Table 3 reveals that the value of αn_a decreases with increasing temperature. The polarographic reduction of acetophenone under the present experimental conditions is well established as a two-electron reduction process and therefore n_a , the number of electrons involved in the rate determining step, can either be 1 or 2. Since the decrease in αn_a values is indiscrete and at no stage the two consecutive values vary by a factor of 2, the possibility of the decrease in the value of αn_a being due to a change in n_a may be ruled out. Thus it can be safely concluded that it is the α which is decreasing. A decrease in the value of α implies that the transfer of electron/electrons is made increasingly difficult. In other words the electrode reaction of acetophenone is rendered increasingly irreversible with increasing temperature. The value of α derived for the reduction of acetophenone is in harmony with the conclusion arrived at on the basis of αn_a values, that $\alpha < 0.5$ at $n=2$ regarded as a condition for total irreversibility.

The $k_{p,h}^0$ value, contrary to the expectation of irreversibility, increases with increase in temperature. Meites^{1,2} has also hinted at the limitation of $k_{p,h}$ in interpreting the results. As a matter of fact,

it is the $k_{s,h}$ (the standard rate constant), the value of which determines the extent of irreversibility of a certain electrode reaction. Unfortunately $k_{s,h}$ could not be determined in the present study as it is not possible to know the value of standard electrode potential for acetophenone. Substituting the value of D from Stokes-Einstein equation, in the Ilkovic equation, we get

$$I_d = 607 \text{ ncm}^{2/3} t^{1/6} \left(\frac{3.32 \times 10^{-5}}{V_m^{1/3} \eta} \right)^{1/2} \quad \dots (7)$$

Assuming that the diffusing particles are spherically symmetrical, one obtains the relation

$$I_d = 607 \text{ ncm}^{2/3} t^{1/6} \left[\frac{3.32 \times 10^{-5}}{4/3\pi r^3 N \eta} \right]^{1/2} \quad \dots (8)$$

Equation (8) can be given in the form

$$r = \frac{K^2}{I_d^2 \eta}$$

where $K = (2.996 \text{ ncm}^{2/3} t^{1/6}) 10^{-4}$.

The data shown in Table 4 indicate that the radius, r , of the reducible species decreases as the temperature increases, indicating that the solvation of acetophenone molecules by the solvent gets destroyed at higher temperatures.

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References

1. R. PASTERNAK, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1948, **31**, 753.
2. M. ASHWORTH, *Colln. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1948, **13**, 229.
3. K. GANAPATHY and M. RAMANUJAM, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, **16A**, 532.
4. I. M. KOLTHOFF and J. J. LINGANE, "Polarography", 2nd Edn., Interscience Publishers, New York, 1952, Vol. 1, p. 396.
5. L. MEITES, "Polarographic Techniques", Interscience Publishers, New York, 1965, p. 241.
6. A. A. VLECK, *Colln. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1959, **24**, 3538.
7. P. DELHAY and J. E. STRASSNER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5219.
8. J. KOUTECKY, *Colln. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1953, **18**, 596.
9. L. MEITES and Y. ISRAEL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4903.
10. J. E. STRASSNER and P. DELAHAY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 6232.
11. L. MEITES, "Polarographic Techniques", Interscience Publishers, New York, 1965, p. 291.
12. L. MEITES, "Polarographic Techniques", Interscience Publishers, New York, 1965, p. 295.